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Supporting information for
Cognitive capacity and control in the evolution of intelligence

Submission to PNAS

Guide to Supporting Information

This document *SI Appendix* outlines derivation and results.

All model derivations, plotting, and experimental materials available through our [repository](#).

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52 1 Cognitive resource allocation dynamics

53

54 An observer has memory resources distributed among m items so that their resource distribution
 55 is $x = [x_1, \dots, x_m]^T$. The resources allocated to any one item must be positive $x_i \geq 0$, with the
 56 sum of allocations being the observer's overall memory capacity $\eta = \sum_{i=1}^m x_i$. In particular, $x \in$
 57 $\Omega^m \subset \mathbb{R}^m$, where Ω^m is a regular m -simplex.

58

59 The probability of recalling an item i is a function F that increases monotonically with the
 60 resources allocated to it x_i . However, recall can never be perfect, so there are diminishing

61 returns. That is, $F: [0, \eta] \rightarrow [0, 1)$, such that $\frac{dF}{dx_i} > 0$ and $\frac{d^2F}{dx_i^2} < 0$ for all x_i . Therefore, we use the

62 convenient form: $F(x_i) = 1 - e^{-x_i}$.

63

64 Given the cued item has probability $q \in [1/m, 1]$ of being required to be recalled, the expected
 65 recall over cue presentations is:

$$R(x) = qF(x_1) + \frac{(1-q)}{(m-1)} \sum_{j=2}^m F(x_j) \quad (\text{S1})$$

66

67 There is a single optimum resource allocation $\hat{x} = \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in \Omega^m} R$. This can be found by using the

68 method of Lagrange, by using the constraint $\eta = \sum_{i=1}^m x_i$ and solving $\nabla R = \alpha \nabla [x_1 + \dots + x_m -$

69 $\eta]$, where α is the Lagrange multiplier. On our domain, Ω^m , the Hessian of the Lagrangian is

70 negative semidefinite:

$$H[\mathcal{L}(R)] = \begin{bmatrix} -qe^{-x_1} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{(1-q)}{(m-1)}e^{-x_2} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & -\frac{(1-q)}{(m-1)}e^{-x_m} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{S2})$$

71 That is, eigenvalues appear along the diagonal, and they are always all negative or zero.
 72 Therefore, $R(x)$ is concave subject to our constraints, with a unique global maximum at \hat{x} .
 73
 74 The optimal allocation for the cued item 1, and the optimal of any of the other j items, are
 75 respectively:

$$\hat{x}_1 = \frac{\eta}{m} + \frac{(m-1)}{m} \ln \left((m-1) \frac{q}{(1-q)} \right) \quad (\text{S3})$$

$$\hat{x}_j = \frac{\eta}{m} - \frac{1}{m} \ln \left((m-1) \frac{q}{(1-q)} \right) \quad (\text{S4})$$

76 As the reliability of q increases it is optimal to allocate more resources to the cued item. It is also
 77 ideal to allocate more resources to the cued item when m increases because the a priori
 78 probability of remembering any item goes down, meaning the cue carries more information. As η
 79 increases it is optimal to have a more uniform distribution of resources; this is due to the
 80 diminishing returns of improving the recall. New capacity can improve the recall of the cued
 81 item relatively less than the un-cued items. When a cue provides no information ($q = 1/m$)
 82 about the item to be recalled, control pushes resources towards a uniform distribution $\hat{x} =$
 83 $\left[\frac{\eta}{m}, \dots, \frac{\eta}{m} \right]^T$; this recovers pure retention and the situation before a cue has arrived. When a cue is
 84 perfectly reliable ($q = 1$) control pushes all resources towards the cued item $\hat{x} = [\eta, \dots, 0]^T$.

85 The optimum resource allocation goal \hat{x} is a desired setpoint that cognitive control pushes
 86 resource allocation towards. Given \hat{x} is a global maximizer, expected recall increases by moving
 87 x along as straight a path as possible towards \hat{x} . This justifies the general form of our resource
 88 dynamics equation, in which direct motion towards \hat{x} occurs at a rate given by cognitive control
 89 $\kappa \in [0, \infty)$, under the constraint that capacity $\eta \in (0, \infty)$ is constant:

$$\frac{dx_i}{dt} = \kappa(\hat{x}_i - x_i) + \varepsilon_i - \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m \kappa(\hat{x}_j - x_j) + \varepsilon_j \quad (\text{S5})$$

90 This is the Langevin form of a stochastic differential equation in which Gaussian white noise is
 91 continuously added to deterministic dynamics (1). In particular, noise is added independently to
 92 the allocation for each item i . The second component of Eq. S5 enforces that capacity is constant
 93 for a given observer, by subtracting the mean change in resources. To model forgetting, when the
 94 process reaches a face of the boundary $\partial\Omega^m$ it remains confined there, this continues until
 95 vertices are reached as final absorbing states. Therefore, we have defined a truncated Ornstein-
 96 Uhlenbeck process.

97

98 The deterministic dynamics of Eq. S5 produce monotonic convergence to the desired setpoint,
 99 because the action of control is continuously scaled by the remaining distance. To illustrate, the
 100 deterministic solution for the remaining distance in each component is $|x_i(t) - \hat{x}_i| =$
 101 $|x_i(0) - \hat{x}_i|e^{-\kappa t}$. From any starting point the distance diminishes exponentially, with larger κ
 102 always increasing the rate of correction. In the next section, we show Eq. S5 in fact defines a
 103 feedback controller that continuously corrects deviations towards the setpoint even in the
 104 presence of noise.

105

106 We conceive of the resources determining recall at the cognitive level, making few commitments
 107 about the resources' neural implementation. That is, we follow empirically successful models of
 108 working memory that find postulating the allocation of a finite resource explains interference and
 109 memory decay as items increase, with animals eventually forgetting (2). Our model captures
 110 these broad features of memory without detailing the degree to which they are underpinned by
 111 neural spiking or changes in neural connectivity (3, 4). We simply assume that constraints
 112 emerge that limit performance. As we focus on the broad functions of working memory, we also
 113 abstract away how different memory systems interact (e.g., episodic and semantic memory), and
 114 distinctions in how their resources operate (5, 6). Understanding this interaction is key for future
 115 research examining how evolution guides the progression from performing a task to learning the
 116 task solution and retaining it in long-term storage. Future research should also examine how
 117 control strategies such as chunking enable more efficient use of available capacity (7), and how
 118 such strategies shape capacity evolution.

119

120 **2 Resource allocation dynamics via optimal control theory**

121

122 Our resource dynamics equation also arises naturally as an approximate solution to a family of
 123 optimal control problems (8). To illustrate, consider a deterministic scenario where control input
 124 u directly adjusts to resource allocation $\frac{dx}{dt} = u$, but producing control input uses energy,
 125 suffering a penalty $\frac{1}{2}u^\top u$. Further, take the typical approach of producing a quadratic
 126 approximation of the reward function around the desired setpoint:

$$R(x) \approx R(\hat{x}) + \frac{1}{2} (\hat{x} - x)^\top \nabla_x^2 R(\hat{x}) (\hat{x} - x) \quad (\text{S6})$$

127 Continuing the illustration, let the objective be maximizing the average reward over a time
 128 period T :

$$\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \left(R(\hat{x}) + \frac{1}{2} (\hat{x} - x)^\top \nabla_x^2 R(\hat{x}) (\hat{x} - x) - \frac{1}{2} u^\top u \right) dt \quad (\text{S7})$$

129 This implies the Hamilton–Jacobi–Bellman equation for value function V :

$$0 = \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \max_u \left\{ \frac{1}{2} (\hat{x} - x)^\top \nabla_x^2 R(\hat{x}) (\hat{x} - x) - \frac{1}{2} u^\top u + \nabla_x V^\top u \right\} \quad (\text{S8})$$

130 Here, u must obey the constraint $\sum_{j=1}^m u_j = 0$ because capacity does not change. Together, this
 131 formulates a standard linear-quadratic regulator problem that can be solved using the Riccati
 132 equation (8, pp. 88-89). The resulting optimal control law is:

$$\hat{u} = \kappa A (\hat{x} - x) \quad (\text{S9})$$

133 Here, the projection that keeps capacity constant is achieved by the matrix:

$$A = I_m - \frac{1}{m} \mathbf{1}_m \mathbf{1}_m^\top \quad (\text{S10})$$

134 Substitution reveals that the optimal control law \hat{u} is the deterministic version of our resource
 135 dynamics equation (Eq S5) written in matrix form. In particular, I_m is the identity matrix and $\mathbf{1}_m$
 136 is an all-ones vector. To disambiguate terms, what we call *cognitive control* κ is the ability to
 137 change resource allocation, the *optimal control law* \hat{u} is a policy for changing resource
 138 allocation. Taking a control theory lens, κ will generally be a function of model parameters (e.g.,
 139 m, q, t) that depend on assumptions about the specific scenario. However, to keep our model
 140 simple, we take κ to be a fixed value that is set genetically that evolves as part of our
 141 evolutionary model.

142

143

144

145 3 Time course of cognitive processing events

146

147 We assume that the observer's initial resource allocation $x(0)$ is drawn from a uniform

148 distribution over our state space Ω^m (a regular m -simplex), which is equivalent to

149 $\frac{x(0)}{\eta} \sim \text{Dirichlet}(\mathbf{1}_m)$. That is, we assume maximum uncertainty about the starting resource

150 allocation (9, pp. 409-425). Before the cue arrives, the observer has no information about the

151 item to be recalled, so control moves resources towards $\hat{x}_{\text{precue}} = \left[\frac{\eta}{m}, \dots, \frac{\eta}{m}\right]^T$. In the time after

152 the cue arrives, control moves resources towards $\hat{x}_{\text{postcue}} = \hat{x}(\eta, m, q)$ (Eqs. S3 and S4).

153 Although control processes attempt to maintain an optimal resource allocation distribution,

154 eroding noise means that items are forgotten. In particular, from the first point in time that no

155 resources are allocated to an item i it is forgotten and cannot be reallocated. This means that $x_i =$

156 0 is an absorbing boundary. Given enough time, the system always reaches an absorbing state

157 with all η resources allocated to a single item, and 0 allocated to the others. So far, we have

158 formulated a cognitive model that is rich enough to fit empirical trends in working memory tasks

159 (see forerunners, (10–12)).

160 4 Fitness function

161

162 We assume successful recall leads to benefits, with superior capacity or control incurring greater

163 investment costs paid regardless of correct recall:

$$W(\eta, \kappa) = \bar{R}(\eta, \kappa) - c(\eta + \kappa) \quad (\text{S11})$$

164 Here, $\bar{R}(\eta, \kappa)$ is the expected recall taken over randomness during cognitive processing due to:

165 (1) initial resource allocations, (2) accrued noise, (3) variation in the time recall must be

166 produced. For simplicity, we assume a separation of timescales between fast cognitive processing

167 and slow evolution on traits, and that environmental stochasticity is stationary and non-
 168 fluctuating.

169 **5 Finding evolutionary optimum**

170

171 We developed an understanding of our evolutionary model's predictions by simulation and
 172 parameter sweeps. Our model of cognitive resource dynamics is not solvable in closed-form, and
 173 so we used Monte Carlo simulation. In particular, we can write the cognitive resource dynamic
 174 equation (Eq S5) in Ito form (1):

$$dx = \kappa A(\hat{x} - x) dt + A dB \quad (\text{S12})$$

$$A = I_m - \frac{1}{m} \mathbf{1}_m \mathbf{1}_m^\top \quad (\text{S13})$$

175 Here, dB is the stochastic increment and A maintains the constraint that capacity is constant. For
 176 simulation, we can leverage the closed-form Ornstein-Uhlenbeck transition (13) to give the
 177 discretized form:

$$\Delta x = (1 - e^{-\kappa \Delta t}) A(\hat{x} - x) + \sqrt{\frac{1 - e^{-2\kappa \Delta t}}{2\kappa}} A \varepsilon_t \quad (\text{S14})$$

$$\varepsilon_t \sim \text{Normal}(0, I_m) \quad (\text{S15})$$

178 To handle absorbing boundaries, we replace A with the following matrix that reduces dimension
 179 and appropriately rescales when an item is forgotten:

$$A' = \text{diag}(a) - \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^m a_i} \text{diag}(a) \text{diag}(a)^\top \quad (\text{S16})$$

$$a = [\mathbb{1}\{x_1 > 0\}, \dots, \mathbb{1}\{x_m > 0\}]^\top \quad (\text{S17})$$

180 We assume the observer must produce recall at a random time drawn uniformly from period T ,
181 with the cue occurring at $T/2$. Producing order 10^6 replicates allowed us to approximate
182 expected recall \bar{R} and thereby fitness W .

183

184 We used the covariance matrix adaptation evolutionary strategy algorithm (CMA-ES) (14) to
185 find the values of capacity and control that maximize fitness $(\hat{\eta}, \hat{\kappa})$. This was used as a robust
186 method to find optima, rather than because it has been studied as a way to understand biological
187 evolution (e.g., Wright-Fisher process). However, it demonstrates optima are reachable by an
188 evolutionary process. The CMA-ES converged from different initializations, consistent with our
189 fitness function having a single maximum. The average relative standard error for $(\hat{\eta}, \hat{\kappa})$
190 solutions >0.05 . Supplementary Code S2 contains simulation script. Dataset S1 contains a broad
191 parameter sweep. Dataset S2 sweeps considering broad range of metabolic costs, and Dataset S3
192 sweeps that support findings about information-processing capability and environmental
193 complexity. Dataset S4 sweeps for separate capacity and control costs. Code S1 contains plotting
194 functions. Find within the [repository](#).

195

196

197 **Fig. S1.** Evolutionary capacity and control simulation optima. Examples shown for high and low
 198 values of load (m) and cue reliability (q). The average relative standard error for ($\hat{\eta}$, $\hat{\kappa}$) solutions
 199 >0.05 , so plotted trends are highly representative. In plots, $T=3$.

200 **6 Long-run expected recall approximation**

201

202 We derive an approximate version of expected recall by looking at the long-run distribution of
 203 resources in the absorbing state. Only the simplest stochastic processes can be solved in closed
 204 form, and our full analysis relies on Monte Carlo simulation. However, by making several
 205 convenient assumptions we gain a closed-form solution that provides insights into how capacity
 206 and control interact. That is, the long-run expected recall \tilde{R} we derive in this section can be used
 207 as a tractable approximation to the full dynamics \bar{R} , but is obtained under stronger assumptions.
 208 First, it considers only the 2-item case ($m = 2$), so resources are allocated to either the cued item
 209 or a non-cued item. Second, it considers the resource allocation expected in population after
 210 memories have been held for long time, and all individuals have forgotten one item and allocated
 211 all resources to the other. That is, it uses the absorbing state distribution, abstracting over
 212 transient dynamics. Nonetheless, \tilde{R} provides a window into system behavior that agrees with the
 213 central conclusions from the full model.

214

215 First, we calculate the probability of ending up with resources allocated to the cued item versus
 216 the non-cued item, from a given initial starting allocation (15, pp. 664-667). Our stochastic
 217 differential equation for resource allocation dynamics (Eq S5) can be formulated as a backward
 218 Kolmogorov equation, telling us the probability density p of reaching a given state, conditional
 219 on an initial state. We change coordinate system to have a single state variable $(x_1, x_2) =$
 220 $(y, \eta - y)$, so that y is the amount of resources allocated to the cued item. In particular, y is the
 221 initial state and y' state reached at a time t so that $p(y, t) = P(y'|y, t)$. This leads to the
 222 backward equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} p(y, t) = -\kappa(\hat{y} - y) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} p(y, t) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} p(y, t) \quad (\text{S18})$$

223 Further, focusing on long-run behavior removes the time dependence and produces:

$$0 = -\kappa(\hat{y} - y) \frac{d}{dy} p(y) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2}{dy^2} p(y) \quad (\text{S19})$$

224 This is a linear second-order ordinary differential equation that can be solved with suitable
 225 boundary conditions. Forgetting means that once an item is allocated no resources, it never
 226 recovers in memory. Without loss of generality, we calculate the probability mass of all resources
 227 being allocated to the cued item. This provides suitable boundary conditions: if all resources are
 228 initially allocated to the cued item, the un-cued item is instantaneously forgotten and this never
 229 changes, $p(\eta) = P(\eta|\eta, t) = 1$ and $p(0) = P(\eta|0, t) = 0$. Therefore, Eq S19 can be solved by
 230 reducing the order and integrating to give:

$$p(y) = \frac{\text{erfi}\left((\eta - y)\sqrt{\kappa}\right) + \text{erfi}(\hat{y}\sqrt{\kappa})}{\text{erfi}\left((\eta - \hat{y})\sqrt{\kappa}\right) + \text{erfi}(\hat{y}\sqrt{\kappa})} \quad (\text{S20})$$

231 Here, erfi is the imaginary error function, a strictly increasing function of its input.

232

233 The next step is calculating the probability of all resources ending up allocated to the cued versus
 234 non-cued item, from *any* initial distribution. In the full model, the initial resource allocation is
 235 random, resource allocation dynamics unfold, and then a cue is received which further alters
 236 dynamics. The advantage of our absorbing state analysis is that it provides clear answers to
 237 questions about our model, but it must abstract over these complicated dynamics. We take the
 238 position of maximum uncertainty about how these transient dynamics unfold by assuming a
 239 uniform distribution over the support (9, pp. 409-425). That is, not knowing the true shape, we

240 assume the maximum entropy distribution that introduces the least bias. This means the
 241 probability all resources will be allocated to the cued item is:

$$P(\eta) = \int_0^\eta p(y) \frac{1}{\eta} dy \quad (\text{S21})$$

$$P(\eta) = \frac{\eta - \hat{y}}{\eta} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}\eta\sqrt{\kappa}} \frac{e^{\hat{y}^2\kappa} - e^{(\eta-\hat{y})^2\kappa}}{(\text{erfi}((\eta - \hat{y})\sqrt{\kappa}) + \text{erfi}(\hat{y}\sqrt{\kappa}))} \quad (\text{S22})$$

242
 243 We are now ready to assemble the long-run expected recall \tilde{R} . With probability q the cued item
 244 must be recalled, and has all η resources allocated to it with probability $P(\eta)$, with the
 245 probability of correct recall as a function of allocated resources being $(1 - e^{-\eta})$. Taking the
 246 complement of events for the non-cued item, the long run expected recall is:

$$\tilde{R} = (1 - e^{-\eta})qP(\eta) + (1 - e^{-\eta})(1 - q)(1 - P(\eta)) \quad (\text{S23})$$

247

248 **7 Capacity and control interactions**

249

250 The approximation to expected recall from the previous section S6, allows us to clarify more
 251 about the interaction between capacity and control. We narrow down to this approximation for
 252 model insights, which are easiest to gain if we consider a fully reliable cue ($q = 1$):

$$\tilde{R} = (1 - e^{-\eta}) \frac{e^{(\eta\sqrt{\kappa})^2} - 1}{\sqrt{\pi}(\eta\sqrt{\kappa})\text{erfi}(\eta\sqrt{\kappa})} \quad (\text{S24})$$

253 When capacity and control appear together, they do so in the term $\eta\sqrt{\kappa}$. This means that the
 254 distribution of resources $P(\eta)$ is affected by capacity and control in a way that is synergistic, in
 255 the sense they scale each other. Furthermore, we see confirmation that capacity is likely to be

256 prioritized in improving recall, because the effect of control is diminished by the square root.
 257 Additionally, capacity directly affects recall because the more resources allocated to an item the
 258 better recall ($1 - e^{-\eta}$), whereas control has only an indirect effect via altering the resource
 259 distribution.

260

261 This synergy alongside the greater efficacy of capacity is evident in Fig. S2, which extends on
 262 the main text to show the derivative of long-run expected recall with respect to capacity. As can
 263 be seen using the legend, both derivatives are positive implying synergy. The derivative with
 264 respect to capacity (i.e. the marginal returns) is larger over a greater range of values, so that
 265 greater investment in capacity is likely profitable under a broad range of cost structures. Finally,
 266 we can see that the highest returns happen at intermediate values of capacity and control, so the
 267 strength of the synergy is non-monotonic. Supplemental Dataset S2 contains parameter sweeps
 268 showing that the production of our three regimes is robust, plotting exists in Code S1
 269 (https://github.com/evanrussek/Capacity_and_Control_Experiment_Analysis).

270

271 **Fig. S2.** Efficacy of recall with a change in control $\partial \bar{R} / \partial \kappa$ and capacity $\partial \bar{R} / \partial \eta$.

272 **8 Metabolic costs and why capacity is more efficacious than control**

273

274 Our evolutionary model found that capacity is broadly prioritized for investment. In the previous
 275 section S7, we showed that a central reason for this is that increasing the reservoir of resources
 276 raises the ceiling on the potential for recall. By contrast, the ability to rearrange resources is
 277 contingent, and must make use of the reservoir that is available. A corollary is that passive
 278 storage can evolve, where capacity exists without control. Here, we explain that this capacity
 279 prioritization would arise in a wide range of stochastic processes, in which deterministic forces
 280 that attempt to revert to a point, alongside additive linear Gaussian noise (1). That is, the finding
 281 that capacity should take on larger values than control emerges fundamentally from how capacity
 282 and control are conceived of in our model: *capacity* setting the volume of total resources, with
 283 *control* being the rate of reversion to the optimal allocation against corrupting noise. Storing
 284 information entails metabolic costs due to maintaining the neural substrate, whereas reallocating
 285 information is costly because it requires modulating activity (16). Our model exemplifies a broad
 286 fact about similar stochastic systems. Whether the reverting force results from tightening a
 287 spring, or from gravity pulling a dust particle to the bottom of a water glass, there are
 288 diminishing returns such that doubling the force's strength much less than halves the amplitude
 289 of the noise.

290

291 To illustrate, consider a general Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process. There are closed-forms for the
 292 expected value and standard deviation for this process (13):

$$\mathbb{E}[x(t)|x(0)] = \hat{x}(1 - e^{-\kappa t}) + x(0)e^{-\kappa t} \quad (\text{S25})$$

$$\text{SD}[x(t)|x(0)] = \sqrt{\frac{(1 - e^{-2\kappa t})}{2\kappa}} I_m \quad (\text{S26})$$

293 In our model, \hat{x} the desired setpoint that maximizes recall, so the signal-to-noise ratio the
 294 expected trend in resource allocation as it approaches a desired value, over the stochastic spread
 295 due to noise, $\|\text{SD}[x(t)|x(0)]^{-1}\mathbb{E}[x(t)|x(0)]\|$. After substituting, we find that capacity and
 296 control affect the signal-to-noise such that $\|\text{SD}[x(t)|x(0)]^{-1}\mathbb{E}[x(t)|x(0)]\| \sim \eta\sqrt{\kappa}$. The term
 297 $\eta\sqrt{\kappa}$ describes how capacity and control synergize in their effect on recall, which is why it also
 298 appears in Eq. S24. That is, capacity linearly increases signal-to-noise, whereas control improves
 299 recall by pushing the systems state against noise and therefore is suppressed by the square root.
 300 This square root relationship is a fundamental feature of systems where a linear corrective drift
 301 opposes a diffusive process (1). It arises because control acts by decreasing dispersion, which is
 302 naturally related to the squared distance around the optimum allocation. Therefore, prioritizing
 303 investment in capacity should emerge in a range of models.

304

305 Given that capacity and control synergize according to $\eta\sqrt{\kappa}$, the metabolic cost of control would
 306 have to be substantially cheaper than capacity for our prediction to be reversed with control
 307 being prioritized for investment. This is a particularly strong requirement in cases where species
 308 invest heavily in cognition. In our base model, we assumed the simplest exchange rate between a
 309 unit of investment in capacity and control, with a single linear cost parameter c . As expected
 310 from our mathematical analysis, this model found prioritization of investment in capacity was
 311 broadly favored. That is, much less than half of relative investment went to control, assuming
 312 equivalent per-unit costs (Fig. 2). We further examined an extension to the model with separate
 313 linear costs, capacity c_η and control c_κ . This robustly supported the prediction of capacity

314 prioritization (Fig. S3). Consistent with this hypothesis, our preliminary experimental data also
315 found both humans and rhesus monkeys displayed more inferred units of capacity than control.
316 Nonetheless, our work has opened a path to test how broadly this holds, and the conditions for
317 reversal that control be exceedingly cheap. Testing our model in the context of empirical
318 measurements of metabolic costs appears an enlightening next step. For instance, developing a
319 large brain densely populated by neurons may be more costly than the transient neural
320 modulation and gating that may underpin attention (17).

321

322 We formally define capacity and control in terms of natural variables that arise within our
323 dynamic systems model. Further, we assume simple linear metabolic costs, minimally capturing
324 the notion that costs increase proportionally with investment in these natural variables. This lays
325 the groundwork for other instantiations. For instance, defining capacity and control directly in
326 terms of information-theoretic quantities, or considering nonlinear biologically-inspired cost
327 functions.

328

329

330 **Fig. S3.** Separate capacity and control costs. Control cost varies down rows, capacity costs vary
 331 on horizontal axis. Costs on a cognitive component reduce that component. Capacity takes on
 332 larger values than control, unless control extremely cheap. Three regime structure emerges. Plot
 333 sets $(m, q, T) = (4, 1, 3)$.

334 9 Scale of capacity and control

335

336 Capacity η is a dimensionless quantity representing the amount of cognitive resource that sets the
337 maximum possible allocation to any item x_i or the total amount across all items. Given the recall
338 function for a given item $F(x_i) = 1 - e^{-x_i}$, capacity has a concrete meaning in terms of
339 increasing recall; the first unit of capacity allocated increases recall from 0 to $1 - e^{-1}$, the
340 second from $1 - e^{-1}$ to $1 - e^{-2}$, and so on. Control κ has units of $[\text{time}]^{-1}$ so is a rate constant,
341 which is clear from our resource dynamics equation Eq S5. By changing the rate of approach of
342 resources $x(t)$ to the optimal allocation, control κ is related to observable trends by being
343 involved in changing recall over time. As T is the maximum time period, κT is a dimensionless
344 quantity that gives the amount of control action that can happen within that period.

345 10 Experimental test methods

346

347 Our experimental study was preregistered prior to the collection of data (<https://osf.io/gnf6h>).

348 The human study protocol was approved by the Princeton University Institutional Review
349 Board. Behavioral data and statistical analysis code is available through [repository](#).

350

351 **Participants.** Participants were recruited through the online platform Prolific

352 (<https://www.prolific.com/>) and were required to be English-speaking adults (≥ 18 years)

353 residing in the United States and to have ≥ 90 % approval ratings. Only participants using desktop
354 or laptop computers were allowed. All participants provided informed consent online before
355 beginning the task. Participants were compensated \$5.25 USD for the 30-min experiment and
356 received a performance-contingent bonus of \$0.015 USD per correct response.

357
 358 Following our preregistered sampling plan, we collected 360 participants. Of these, 14
 359 participants were excluded based on pre-defined exclusion rules (Figs. S4 and S5). The exclusion
 360 rules aimed to remove participants that either had near-chance performance or demonstrated a
 361 high degree of bias in their response (e.g. tended to always report that they had seen the image).
 362 To identify these characteristics, we computed for each participant the signal detection theory
 363 metrics, sensitivity (d') and bias (criterion, c). These metrics were measured by using both cue
 364 valid and invalid trials, along with non-match trials (Fig. 4), to compute a hit rate and false-alarm
 365 rate using the standard log-linear (add-0.5) correction (18, 19). We then excluded participants
 366 with either near-chance sensitivity ($d' < .25$) or high bias ($|c| > .50$). This resulted in the
 367 removal of 14 participants, leaving us with 346 for our main analysis. We included the data of all
 368 10 rhesus macaques (*Macaca mulatta*) collected previously who took part across 6 experiments
 369 conducted by Brady & Hampton (10), who were outside our exclusion ranges.

370

371

372 **Fig. S4.** Distribution of sensitivity and criterion values for human participants. In our main
 373 analysis, we only analyze cue valid and invalid trials (probed image was in the original set), it is

374 therefore important to remove participants who show extreme bias in their responses, as this
 375 could mask as higher or lower overall accuracy. Additionally, we remove participants that display
 376 near chance accuracy. To separate bias from sensitivity, we use both match and non-match trials
 377 to compute signal detection theory measures of sensitivity (d') and bias (criterion, c) for each
 378 participant. Based on our pre-registered thresholds, we removed participants with $d' < .25$ and
 379 $|c| > .5$ (vertical dashed lines in either plot). Overall, 7 human participants were removed based
 380 on d' and 8 were removed based on criterion (with one participant being flagged for both), for a
 381 total of 14 removals out of 360 participants.
 382

383

384 **Fig. S5.** Distribution of d' and c (criterion) values for rhesus macaques. Vertical lines show
 385 exclusion thresholds (none removed).
 386

387 **Stimuli.** For comparability with the monkey data we used the original stimulus set provided by
 388 Brady & Hampton. The items to be recalled were drawn from nine colored photographs of
 389 natural scenes. Each image subtended 146×139 px and was presented within a 218×196 px
 390 white frame on a black background. Four peripheral frames were arranged around a central
 391 frame in a cross configuration. On each trial two, three or four images were presented
 392 simultaneously at distinct peripheral locations, depending on the load condition. The same
 393 stimuli were used for all participants, but their positions and assignments to trial types were
 394 randomized. Stimuli were presented via the *jsPsych* library (v 7.3.1) (20) running in participants'
 395 web browsers.

396

397 **Trial structure.** To ensure comprehension, participants first read written instructions followed
398 by a short instruction quiz. Participants were required to answer every quiz question correctly
399 before beginning the task. In the task, each trial followed the sequence of events used by Brady
400 & Hampton (Fig. 4):

401

402 1. Ready prompt: A ready screen at the beginning of every trial, shown as a green rectangle
403 at fixation.

404 2. Encoding phase: Two, three or four images were presented simultaneously at distinct
405 peripheral locations for 2,000 ms.

406 3. Pre-cue delay: A blank screen was shown for 300, 700 or 1100 ms.

407 4. Retro-cue: A dashed frame blinked twice around one peripheral location. Each blink
408 lasted 150 ms on, 150 ms off and 150 ms on (total 450 ms).

409 5. Post-cue delay: A second blank interval of variable duration followed. The sum of
410 pre-cue and post-cue delay was held constant at 1,350 ms.

411 6. Recall test. A single test image appeared at screen center; participants had up to 3,000 ms
412 to press “J” if the image had appeared in the study array or “F” if it was new. Correct
413 responses triggered a “correct” tone and displayed + \$0.10 for 1.5 s; incorrect responses
414 played an error tone and displayed \$0.00 for 1.5 s.

415 7. Inter-trial interval. After the 1.5 s feedback display, a blank interval of 3.5 s followed
416 correct responses (total 5.0 s ITI), and a blank interval of 5.5 s followed incorrect
417 responses (total 7.0 s timeout) before the next trial started.

418

419 Our statistical model makes predictions about accuracy on cue valid or invalid trials where the
420 recall test image matched an image in the encoding array. Non-match trials are used to exclude
421 participants (as outlined in *Participants*).

422

423 Our study comprised the following independent variables, which pilot testing suggested would
424 support estimating capacity and control:

425

- 426 1. Cue validity: On valid trials, the cued location accurately signaled which image would be
427 probed. On invalid trials, the cued location did not match the image that was probed. This
428 was varied within-participant
- 429 2. Cue reliability q : The probability that a match trial was valid or invalid. Cue reliability
430 was varied between-participant, being either .70 or .92, and held constant for all trials for
431 a single participant.
- 432 3. Load m : The number of images the participant needed to remember, being either 2, 3 or 4
433 images. We used a mixed approach to manipulation to improve power while ruling out
434 interference effects. For half of sampled participants, load was varied within-participant
435 (in 40 trial blocks; order counterbalanced across participants). In the other half, load was
436 varied between-participants (and held constant for a single participant).
- 437 4. Cue time (Pre-cue delay) was the amount of time between stimulus offset and the cue.
438 This was either 300 ms, 700 ms, or 1100 ms. Cue time was manipulated in the same
439 mixed way as load but in the opposite half of the sample. In the model, this manipulated
440 the proportion of the total time period T before the cue.
- 441 5. Species: comprised of rhesus monkeys and humans.

442

443 Note that in cases where a variable (either load or cue time) was manipulated block-wise within
444 participant, the length of that block was always 40 trials and included 20 match and 20 non-
445 match trials. Valid and invalid trials were distributed as evenly as possible across the three
446 blocks, such that in $q = .70$ case, there were 6 invalid trials within each block and in the $q =$
447 $.92$ case there was 1 invalid trial in the first block and 2 invalid trials in the second and third
448 block. Block order was counterbalanced across participants.

449 **11 Experimental test statistical analyses**

450

451 **Visualization of performance over conditions.** To illustrate participant performance, we
452 computed mean accuracy for each participant for each trial-type in which they participated. Fig.
453 S6 shows across-participant mean accuracy in each trial-type with 95% between-participant
454 confidence intervals. To highlight the effect of cue time, load and cue validity, and interactions of
455 these with cue validity, we provide additional plots (Figs. S6, S7 and S8). For these, we
456 computed within participant accuracy for a given cue time (or load or cue validity) for valid and
457 invalid trials, collapsing over the other two variables, and compute between-participant mean and
458 95% confidence intervals over those means.

459

460 **Generalized linear mixed effects model.** Preliminary to our main statistical model, we fit
461 separate binomial generalized linear mixed effects models of human and rhesus macaques recall
462 performance on match trials (Tables S1 and S2). Models were fit using the [MixedModels.jl](#)
463 package for the Julia programming language (21). For humans, we fit a model predicting trial
464 accuracy as a function of Cue Validity, Cue Reliability, Cue Time, Load, and the interaction of

465 Cue Validity with Cue Reliability, Cue Time and Load. Random effects were included for
466 intercepts and for all slopes, except for those involving Cue Reliability, which was only
467 manipulated between-participant. For rhesus macaques, because cue reliability was not varied,
468 we fit the same model, but removed terms involving cue reliability. Model coefficients' p -values
469 were obtained from the package and reflect Wald tests using a standard normal approximation.

470

471 **Statistical model estimating capacity and control.** Capacity and control parameters for the
472 recall model were estimated for either species using hierarchical Bayesian inference, such that
473 group-level priors for either species were used to regularize participant-level estimates for
474 participants from that species. The joint posterior over group and participant-level parameters
475 was approximated using No-U-Turn Sampling (22) as implemented in Stan (23). Four chains
476 with 2000 samples (1000 discarded as burn-in) were run for a total of 4000 posterior samples.
477 Chain convergence was determined by ensuring that the Gelman-Rubin statistics were close to 1
478 (all were less than 1.017) and that there were no divergent transitions. Bulk/tail ESS were
479 generally ample (many >700), with a few lower—but acceptable—values for $\beta_{\text{human},\eta}$ (~ 303) and
480 $\sigma_{\text{human},\kappa}$ (~ 222). A full description of the parameterization and implementation of the model and
481 choice of priors can be found in SI Appendix, section 13. From each drawn sample, we extracted
482 species-level posterior distributions for (log-transformed) mean capacity and control values as
483 well as how they vary across participants within each species. These posterior distributions were
484 then used to calculate derived quantities and between-species contrasts (see SI Appendix, section
485 13 for full model and computation of derived quantities).

486

487 **Posterior predictive accuracy plots.** We generated posterior predictive summaries of accuracy
488 using parameter draws from the fitted hierarchical model. To do this, we drew 200 samples of
489 species-level group mean, scale parameters and correlation factor. For each selected draw of
490 species-level parameters, we sampled sets of participant-level parameters equal to the number of
491 individuals in the sample. This set of species-level parameters were used to compute expected
492 accuracy on each trial-type performed by that species. Specifically, for each condition (specified
493 by cue reliability, cue timing and load), we computed expected accuracy for each condition for
494 valid and invalid trials in that condition, for all sampled participants in that species and average
495 across participants to obtain the species-level posterior predictive mean for that draw. We
496 aggregate the draw-wise means to show the posterior predictive mean and the 95% credible
497 interval over draws.

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509 **12 Experimental test results**

510

511 **Table S1.** Results from binomial generalized linear mixed effects model of human recall
 512 performance. We fit a binomial generalized linear mixed effects model to predict trial accuracy
 513 as a function of Cue Validity, Cue Reliability, Cue Time, Load, and the interaction of Cue
 514 Validity with Cue Reliability, Cue Time and Load. Random effects were included for intercepts
 515 and for all slopes, except for those involving Cue Reliability, which was only manipulated
 516 between-participant. The model predicts negative effects of Load and positive effects of cue
 517 validity on accuracy. Additionally, it predicts that cue validity interacts with cue reliability, cue
 518 time, and load. We observed significant main effects of load and cue validity, in the direction
 519 predicted by the model. With regard to interactions, we noted in our pre-registration that based
 520 on prior simulation of the model, we were likely underpowered to observe these effects. Despite
 521 this, we observed significant interaction of cue validity and cue reliability. Furthermore, although
 522 non-significant, the other two interaction effects are in the predicted direction.

Predictor	Coef.	SE	z	P
Intercept	2.13	0.08	26.11	< .001
Cue Validity	1.35	0.13	10.60	< .001
Cue Reliability	-2.38	0.71	-3.34	< .001
Cue Time	-0.05	0.24	-0.22	.826
Load	-0.25	0.06	-4.26	< .001
Cue Validity × Cue Reliability	4.01	1.11	3.61	< .001
Cue Validity × Cue Time	-0.36	0.37	-0.99	.321
Cue Validity × Load	0.17	0.11	1.60	.110

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530 **Table S2.** Results from binomial generalized linear mixed effects model of Rhesus Macaque
 531 recall performance.

Predictor	Coef.	SE	z	P
Intercept	0.93	0.08	11.32	< .001
Cue Validity	0.19	0.13	1.47	.142
Cue Time	-0.51	0.20	-2.50	.012
Load	-0.12	0.14	-0.89	.371
Cue Validity \times Cue Time	-1.01	0.72	-1.41	.159
Cue Validity \times Load	-0.64	0.26	-2.51	.012

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535 **Fig. S6.** Mean accuracy of humans and rhesus macaques on each condition. Error bars reflect
 536 95% confidence intervals. Means and confidence intervals are computed between participants.

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Fig. S7. Posterior predictive accuracy of humans and rhesus macaques on each condition, from model fit to data.

545

546 **Fig. S8.** Mean accuracy on match trials as a function of load and cue validity for Human
 547 Participants (left) and Model posterior predictions (Right). Mean accuracy collapses over cue
 548 reliability and cue timing. The model predicts both a negative main effect of load as well as an
 549 interaction of load and cue validity. We detected a main effect of load (Table S1). The interaction
 550 effect of load and cue validity was in the predicted direction but was not statistically significant.
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557 **Fig. S9.** Mean accuracy against pre-cue timing and cue validity for humans (left) and model
 558 posterior predictions (Right). Mean accuracy collapses over cue reliability and load. The model
 559 predicts a negative interaction of cue validity and pre-cue timing. We detected a main effect of
 560 cue validity (Table S1). The interaction of cue validity and cue timing was in the predicted
 561 direction but was not statistically significant.

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568 **Fig. S10.** Mean accuracy on match trials as a function of cue reliability and cue validity for
 569 human participants (left) and model posterior predictions (Right). Mean accuracy collapses over
 570 cue timing and load. The model predicts a positive interaction of cue reliability and cue validity
 571 timing. We observed a significant interaction of cue reliability and cue validity in human data
 572 (Table S1).

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581 **Fig. S11 Proportion investment in control for either species.** Humans invest more in control
 582 as a proportion of their total investment than rhesus macaques. Figures show posterior
 583 distributions over the proportion of total investment that members of either species invest in
 584 control. For both humans and rhesus macaques, at the group-level, capacity exceeded control
 585 (Posterior Capacity - Control in Humans: $M = 6.54$; 95% CrI [4.70, 9.44]; Rhesus Macaques: M
 586 $= 3.99$; 95% CrI [3.15, 4.92]). Humans however, invested more in control as a proportion of total
 587 investment than Rhesus Macaques (Posterior Difference in Proportion Control, Humans - Rhesus
 588 Macaques; $M = .21$ 95% CrI [0.09, 0.30]).
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599 **13 Full statistical model and derived quantities**

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601 To estimate the capacity and control of humans and monkeys, we fit the recall model to retro-cue
 602 performance data. Our statistical model tested predictions of the theoretical model by
 603 implementing the expected recall function \bar{R} (SI Appendix, sections 1-3). Because direct Monte
 604 Carlo marginalization is computationally intensive and incompatible with deterministic
 605 likelihood optimization, we use a neural-network surrogate of \bar{R} (24). The statistical model was
 606 fit with Stan (23); the neural network was trained in Scikit-learn (25) .

607

608 **Expected recall.** We take the expected recall of a participant, j , to be a function of their capacity
 609 and control, as well as condition:

$$610 \quad \bar{R}_j: (\eta_j, \kappa_j, \nu; q, t_{\text{pre}}, m, k) \rightarrow [0,1].$$

611 \bar{R}_j is the expected recall accuracy of the process described in SI sections 1-3. Here c denotes cue
 612 validity; q denotes cue reliability, t_{pre} is pre-cue time and load m denotes load, η_j denotes
 613 capacity of participant j , κ_j denotes control of participant j . To adapt the model to fully describe
 614 human and monkey experimental data, we introduce an additional parameter, ν , which controls
 615 per-timestep noise in the diffusion process, by scaling each noise term in (S5) by $\sqrt{\nu}$. To improve
 616 identifiability of η_j and κ_j , we assume ν does not vary across participants and is sampled from
 617 the following prior distribution,

$$618 \quad \log(\nu) \sim \mathcal{N}(.55, 0.75^2).$$

619 This specific prior was chosen so that it would be centered at the geometric mean of the
 620 surrogate bounds for ν (described below), so as to keep all prior mass on ν around where the
 621 surrogate was trained, and to provide a spread that would be weakly informative.

622 **Surrogate for \bar{R} (likelihood approximation network).** There is no simple closed form for \bar{R}_j
 623 because it requires marginalizing over noisy events at each time-step (equation S5). We therefore
 624 approximate \bar{R}_j with a simulation-trained surrogate (24). To train the surrogate, we first simulate
 625 a large dataset by sampling 30,000 parameter triples (η, κ, ν) . For each triple and for each task
 626 condition $(q, t_{\text{pre}}, m, k)$, we computed \bar{R} as the mean of 800 noisy simulations. We then trained
 627 a feedforward multi-layer perceptron (two hidden layers, 128 units each) to predict \bar{R} from
 628 $(\eta, \kappa, \nu, q, t_{\text{pre}}, m, k)$, minimizing mean squared error on logit-transformed probabilities. The
 629 resulting network provides a deterministic, computationally efficient surrogate that we embed in
 630 the likelihood.

631 **Observation model.** To separate attentional lapses from extra-binomial variability, we use two
 632 components. First, we mix the surrogate-predicted accuracy with chance:

$$633 \quad \mu_{j,k,q,t_{\text{pre}},m} = (1 - \epsilon_j) \bar{R}_j(k, q, t_{\text{pre}}, m) + \epsilon_j \cdot 0.5.$$

634

635 Second, we model counts with a Beta–Binomial in mean–concentration form:

$$636 \quad y_{j,k,q,t_{\text{pre}},m} \sim \text{BetaBinomial}(n_{j,k,q,t_{\text{pre}},m}, \mu_{j,k,q,t_{\text{pre}},m}, \phi_j),$$

637 where ϕ_j is a participant-level concentration parameter (larger ϕ_j approaches Binomial).

638 Hierarchical structure for capacity and control. Capacity and control vary by species, s . Because
 639 $\eta > 0$ and $\kappa \geq 0$, we model them on the log scale:

$$640 \begin{bmatrix} \log(\eta_j) \\ \log(\kappa_j) \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu} + \mathbf{1}[s(j) = \text{human}] \boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{s(j)})$$

641 Here, $s(j)$ is the species of participant j , $\boldsymbol{\mu} = [\mu_\eta, \mu_\kappa]^\top$ is the monkey baseline; $\boldsymbol{\beta} = [\beta_\eta, \beta_\kappa]^\top$ is
 642 the human–monkey adjustment (species contrast). Priors are

$$643 \boldsymbol{\mu} \sim \mathcal{N}(\bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}, \sigma_\mu^2 \mathbf{I}), \quad \boldsymbol{\beta} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_\beta^2 \mathbf{I}),$$

644 with $(\bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}, \sigma_\mu, \sigma_\beta) = (0, 2.0, 1.0)$. This type of parameterization has been previously
 645 recommended as a way to test for group differences (26).

646

647 Random effects enter via species-specific covariance:

$$648 \boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s) (LL^\top) \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s),$$

649 where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s = [\sigma_{s,\eta}, \tau_{s,\kappa}]^\top \sim \text{Exponential}(\bar{\tau})$ and L is the Cholesky factor of a correlation matrix
 650 with $L \sim \text{LKJ}(\bar{L})$. We use $(\bar{\tau}, \bar{L}) = (1, 2)$.

651

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655 **Hierarchy for dispersion and lapses.** For extra-binomial dispersion, participant-level
 656 concentration parameters have species-level priors:

$$657 \quad \log(\phi_j) \sim \mathcal{N}(\bar{\theta}_{s(j)}, \sigma_{\theta,s(j)}^2), \quad \bar{\theta}_s \sim \mathcal{N}(\log(100), 1.0^2), \quad \psi_{\theta,s} \sim \text{Exponential}(1.0).$$

658 These priors are chosen to put ϕ_j near 100, which places variance as close to Binomial, but not
 659 forced. Participant deviations are $z_{\theta,j} \sim \mathcal{N}(0,1)$ with $\log\phi_j = \bar{\theta}_{s(j)} + \psi_{\theta,s(j)} z_{\theta,j}$.

660 Participant-level lapses follow $\text{logit}(\epsilon_j) \sim \mathcal{N}(\text{logit}(0.02), 1.0^2)$.

661

662 **Derived quantities and comparison.** For hypotheses, because exponentiation induces skewness
 663 in distributions over original-scale values, we focus on species-level geometric means (medians)
 664 of capacity and control on the original scale:

$$665 \quad \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\eta}_s \\ \bar{\kappa}_s \end{bmatrix} = \exp(\boldsymbol{\mu} + \mathbf{1}[s = \text{human}] \boldsymbol{\beta}).$$

666 This focuses values on the typical member of a species. Fig. 5 shows 95% HDI values of $\begin{bmatrix} \bar{\eta}_s \\ \bar{\kappa}_s \end{bmatrix}$ for
 667 either species.

668

669 We additionally compute two derived species-level quantities from posterior draws. First, we
 670 define the proportion of control as the expected fraction of control relative to total resource for a
 671 randomly drawn participant of species s , $p_s^{\text{ctrl}} = \mathbf{E}_j \left[\frac{\kappa_{js}}{(\kappa_{js} + \eta_{js})} \right]$. We approximate this expectation

672 by Monte Carlo averaging across simulated participant effects for each posterior draw: $p_s^{\text{ctrl}} \approx$

673 $\frac{\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\kappa_{js}}{(\kappa_{js} + \eta_{js})}}{N}$. Posterior distributions of p_s^{ctrl} for either species s are shown in Fig. S11.

674 Second, we define information-processing capability (IPC) at a reference condition ($q^* =$

675 $.92, t_{pre}^* = 700 \text{ ms}, m^* = 3$; see section 14, below). Expected recall at this condition is

676 obtained from the surrogate as a mixture of valid and invalid cue probabilities averaged across

677 simulated participants, s : $\bar{R}_s(q^*, t_{pre}^*, m^*) = q^* p_s^{\text{valid}} + (1 - q^*) p_s^{\text{invalid}}$.

678 Here, p_s^{valid} and p_s^{invalid} are the output of the surrogate on valid and invalid trial-types, given

679 reference condition settings and parameters of participant s . Information-processing capability

680 multiplies this expected recall by the available information under set size m (measured in bits):

681
$$IPC_s = H(m^*) \bar{R}_s(q^*, t_{pre}^*, m^*)$$

682
$$H(m) = \log_2 m$$

683 Posterior distributions over IPC_s are show in Fig. S13.

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690 **14 Model comparison of species differences in capacity and control**

691
 692 To provide an additional test that both capacity and control distributions differ between species,
 693 we compared a set of nested hierarchical models which varied in whether the species-level
 694 distributions of capacity η and/or control κ were allowed to differ between rhesus macaques and
 695 humans. Specifically, we fit the following four (nested) variants of the model that differ only in
 696 whether the group-level distribution of $\log(\eta)$ and $\log(\kappa)$ is shared across species or allowed to
 697 differ:

- 698 1. $M_{both-shared}$: both $\log(\eta)$ and $\log(\kappa)$ are drawn from group-level distributions that are
 699 shared between species
- 700 2. $M_{\eta\text{ varies}}$: $\log(\eta)$ is drawn from separate species-specific distribution; $\log(\kappa)$ is drawn
 701 from a distribution shared between species
- 702 3. $M_{\kappa\text{ varies}}$: $\log(\kappa)$ is drawn from separate species-specific distribution; $\log(\eta)$ is drawn
 703 from a distribution shared between species
- 704 4. $M_{both-vary}$: both $\log(\eta)$ and $\log(\kappa)$ are drawn from species-specific group-level
 705 distributions that are shared between species

706
 707 All other model components were identical across variants. We evaluated each variant's
 708 performance using participant-level 5-fold cross validation, holding out entire subjects at a time
 709 (27). Following subject removal (Figs. S4 and S5), our dataset comprised 10 monkeys and 177
 710 humans. We constructed five folds stratified by species such that each fold held 2 monkeys and
 711 35-36 humans, with no overlap between folds and each participant held out exactly once. For
 712 each fold and each model variant, we refit the model using only non-heldout subjects and
 713 computed the held-out log predictive density for each held-out subject by summing the log

714 likelihood contributions across that subject's trials under the posterior draws from the training fit.
 715 Specifically, for held-out subject s , we scored predictive accuracy by summing trialwise log
 716 predictive densities and averaging over posterior draws: $elpd_s = \frac{1}{D} \sum_{d=1}^D \sum_{i \in s} \log p(y_i | \theta^{(d)})$
 717 where i indexes trials belonging to subject s , y_i is the observed trial outcome, and $\theta^{(d)}$ is posterior
 718 draw d from the fit to non-held-out subjects. The overall k -fold expected log predictive density
 719 was then computed as $ELPD = \sum_{s=1}^S elpd_s$, where each subject's $elpd_s$ comes from the fold in
 720 which that subject was held out. For paired comparison between models, we computed per-
 721 subject differences in $elpd_s$ and the total difference as the sum of these across subjects. We also
 722 report the estimated standard error (SE) of the total difference (27).

723

724 Model comparison results are reported in Table S3. We found that the variant allowing both
 725 capacity and control to vary across species $M_{both-vary}$, achieved the best out-of-sample
 726 predictive performance (largest $ELPD$). Relative to $M_{both-vary}$, variants allowing only one
 727 component to vary showed smaller $ELPD$, with modest uncertainty in the corresponding $\Delta ELPD$.
 728 The variant with both components shared, $M_{both-shared}$, was the worst performing. Altogether,
 729 this indicates that both capacity and control contribute to species differences in recall
 730 performance.

731

732 **Table S3.** Results from model-comparison of species-differences in capacity and control.

Model	<i>ELPD</i>	$\Delta ELPD$ (relative to best model)	SE($\Delta ELPD$)
$M_{both-vary}$	-1761.14	0.00	0.00
$M_{\kappa \text{ varies}}$	-1765.66	4.52	3.17
$M_{\eta \text{ varies}}$	-1766.82	5.68	3.05
$M_{both-shared}$	-1785.12	23.98	7.32

733 **15 Complex tasks select for information-processing capability**

734

735 Previous work has emphasized the importance of changes in information processing capability
736 for explaining intelligence (28). Our model distinguishes pure storage capacity from the control
737 strategies that can be used to manipulate stored representations. However, we can also explore
738 how these two factors combine to determine overall information processing capability. We find
739 consistency with prior evolutionary models that show complex tasks select for superior
740 information processing (29–41).

741

742 We measure the *complexity* of a task by the number of bits required to encode it without loss
743 $H(m) = \log_2(m)$. Therefore, we take an information-theoretic definition of complexity as the
744 amount of uncertainty that must be resolved for perfect performance (42). Complex tasks are
745 those for which success is unlikely in the absence of knowledge, leading to a coherent measure
746 that can be applied across tasks faced by animals (32–34). In our model, more information is
747 required when there are more items to remember. This maps to ecological challenges such as
748 tracking the location of multiple food items or group members

749

750 We measure *information-processing capability* as the overall proficiency of the observer
751 considering the combined operation of capacity alongside control by $\bar{R}(\eta, \kappa)H(m)$. That is, often
752 being successful at a complex task implies superior information processing. We think of capacity
753 and control as combining to give an animal's overall information-processing capability. That is,
754 we provide a proxy for information the observer processes about a task as expressed in correct or
755 incorrect recall. Intuitively, the fraction of task information processed is the fraction of trials
756 correct.

757

758 We find that solely increasing the complexity of tasks leads to rudimentary information
 759 processing, in the absence of cues that allow the tracking of task features (Fig. S12). This is
 760 primarily because when an animal must store many items, their a priori probability of correctly
 761 recalling is low, so investing in information processing generates little benefit. It is not simply
 762 the case that a challenging world selects for a larger brain.

763

764 We find informative cues are required to make rich representations profitable (Fig. S12). The
 765 mutual information between the cue and environment is:

$$q \log_2(mq) + (1 - q) \log_2 \left(m \frac{1 - q}{m - 1} \right) \quad (S27)$$

766 Here, the probability a cue indicates the picked item is q , and indicates a non-cued item with
 767 probability $\frac{1-q}{m-1}$. This is the mutual information for an m -ary symmetric channel with uniform
 768 input and accuracy q (9), p. 190). When an observer receives a cue about which item is likely to
 769 lead to a reward, greater control is selected because it now pays to reallocate resources. For
 770 instance, the rustle of a group member cueing that a food item is taken leads the observer to
 771 update their representation. If the scene the observer attempts to encode is also complex, there
 772 are the conditions for substantial joint investment in control alongside capacity. This is because
 773 while the observer must grapple with a complex task that requires significant information to
 774 represent reliable cues allow it to deploy control to gain rewards. Consequently, our model
 775 suggests the hypothesis that amount of information provided by cues about valuable tasks
 776 corresponds to the animal's ability to process information.

777

778

779 **Fig. S12.** Task complexity and cue reliability shape information-processing capability (example
 780 sets $c = .10, T = 3$). The information complexity of the task presented by the environment
 781 $H(m)$ increases with the load of m items, where $H(m) = \log_2(m)$ is the entropy of uninformed
 782 guessing. Cue reliability q (vertical axis) along with the complexity of the environment
 783 (horizontal axis) determines the information carried by the cue (cross-cutting greyscale
 784 contours). Cues carry higher information in uncertain environments with reliable cues. Plotted in
 785 color are features of the animal's cognition: warmer colors indicate higher values of information-
 786 processing capability. High information-processing capability $\bar{R}(\eta, \kappa)H(m)$ evolves when there
 787 are reliable cues to a complex environment, as success often occurs, although a complex
 788 representation is required. Highly informative cues lead to higher information-processing
 789 capability. When cues are unreliable, a complex environment leads to low information-
 790 processing capability because success is rare.

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793 We can also apply the same ideas to the analysis of our empirical data. Using the same metric for

794 information-processing capability, combining accuracy with task complexity, we find that

795 humans have a greater information-processing capability than rhesus monkeys (Fig. S11).

796 Humans express nearly all 1.58 bits possible in the load 3 task. Because task complexity bounds

797 the information processing an animal can express, difficult tasks are required to find the upper

798 limit of a species.

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801 **Fig. S13.** Information-processing capability for humans and rhesus macaques. To obtain a
802 comparable measure for humans and monkeys, we computed expected performance in the
803 condition cue reliability .92, load 3, and pre-cue delay 700 ms, leading to $\bar{R}(\eta, \kappa)H(3)$. Humans
804 had greater information-processing capability than monkeys (M = .40, 95% CrI [0.28, 0.50]).
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816 **References**

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